

Survey on Refactoring for Elixir

FREE AND ENLIGHTENED CONSENT

Title: Refactorings for systems implemented in the Elixir functional language

Institution: DCC / ICEx / UFMG

Responsible researchers:

- Lucas Vegi (lucasvegi@dcc.ufmg.br)

Doctoral student at the Department of Computer Science at UFMG

- Prof. Marco Túlio Valente (mtov@dcc.ufmg.br)

Associate professor at the Department of Computer Science at UFMG

This "Free and Enlightened Consent" contains information about our research. If you have any questions, do not hesitate to ask the responsible researchers.

Evaluation goals: This study aims to understand the main refactoring strategies used in code implemented in the Elixir functional language

Survey information: We will ask you questions about your demographics, positions held, experience with Elixir, and your perception about the refactoring strategies in Elixir (use frequency and impact on system quality)

Data collection and use: The data will be collected through this Google Form. It is estimated that each participant will need a maximum of 20 minutes to complete the answers. This data will be used to promote good practices to improve the quality of code implemented in Elixir. The identities of all participants, as well as their responses, will be kept confidential. You may choose to receive the preliminary results of the study, with the anonymity of data and participants preserved. The results will be published and presented at conferences and scientific journals without revealing the identity of the participants.

If you decide not to participate in the research: You are free to refuse to participate or withdraw your consent at any time. Your decision will not affect any relationship with the evaluators, professors, or the institution responsible for this research.

Compensation: Your participation is voluntary and unpaid. In addition, you will not be charged for participating in this research.

If you have any problems or any other questions about the research: You can contact Lucas Vegi at any time at lucasvegi@dcc.ufmg.br.

If you have questions about the ethical aspects of this research: Contact the Research Ethics Committee of the Federal University of Minas Gerais (COEP-UFMG). Address: Av. Antônio Carlos, 6627. Administrative Unit II – 2nd floor - Room 2005. Pampulha Campus. Belo Horizonte – MG, Brazil. CEP: 31270-901. E-mail: coep@prpq.ufmg.br. Phone: +55 (31) 3409-4592. Opening hours: 09:00 AM to 11:00 AM; 02:00 PM to 04:00 PM (UTC-3).

Risks and measures to minimize them: When answering the questions, you may feel uncomfortable with questions that can bring back bad memories, fear of not knowing the answer, or even being identified. If you feel uncomfortable, you can pause completing the questionnaire and withdraw from participation at any time. The guarantee of data confidentiality ensured by the researchers is limited to the privacy policies of the virtual environment used for data collection (Google Forms). According to Brazilian legislation (Art. 9 of Resolution nº 510/16 of the National Health Council), in case of any damages resulting from your participation in this research, you will have the right to be compensated, under the terms of the Law.

Benefits: This research aims to promote good practices for improving the quality of systems implemented in Elixir, thus justifying its risks.

This survey will be carried out entirely remotely. In this way, [this consent term will be made available in digital copy through this Google Form](#). A copy of this digital consent will be kept by the responsible researchers and you will receive a digital copy via email after signing the term.

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

E-mail *

Seu e-mail

Free and Enlightened Consent (voluntary agreement) *

I declare that I have read the document mentioned above and that I agree to participate as a volunteer, authorizing the anonymous use of the data generated by my participation for the academic purposes described above.

Your full name: *

Sua resposta

Próxima

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Survey on Refactoring for Elixir

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

Demographic questions

How many different projects have you participated in using Elixir? *

- Only one project
- Between 2 and 4 projects
- More than 4 projects

Select your country: *

Elixir experience time: *

- Less than 1 year
- Between 1 and 3 years
- More than 3 years

Your city: *

Sua resposta

Voltar

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Survey on Refactoring for Elixir

Perceptions on the Relevance and Prevalence of refactorings

Refactoring strategies are **code transformations that do not alter a program's behavior**. In our research, we aim to catalog and document refactorings for the Elixir programming language. We would like to know your perception regarding these refactorings.

Therefore, based on your experience, answer the questions below.

[Prevalence] How often do you perform this refactoring in your Elixir systems or see this refactoring being carried out in code implemented with this language?
(1 = it is very rare; 5 = it is very common)

[Relevance] How relevant is this refactoring in Elixir systems? (i.e., when answering consider the potential of this refactoring to have a positive impact on maintainability, comprehensibility, and evolution of Elixir code)
(1 = very low impact and relevance; 5 = high impact and relevance)

Notes:

- Each refactoring is accompanied by a short description and a link containing code examples;
- You don't have to answer all questions items if you don't want to.

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Improving list appending performance]**.

This refactoring aims to improve runtime performance during the concatenation of elements into a list, replacing *tail concatenations* with *head concatenations*, thus increasing the amount of shared memory between the intermediate lists. More details and code examples here: [\[LINK\]](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[From meta to normal function application]**.

This refactoring aims to replace the use of the *Kernel.apply/3* function with direct calls to functions that have modules, names, and parameter lists defined at compile time. More details and code examples here: [\[LINK\]](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Convert nested conditionals to pipeline]**.

This refactoring eliminates nested conditionals used only to control a sequence of function calls, replacing them with pipe operators. The interfaces of functions involved in the pipe are also modified by adding parameters and using pattern matching. More details and code examples here: [\[LINK\]](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Introduce pattern matching over a parameter]**.

This refactoring aims to replace classic conditional structures (e.g., *if*, *unless*, *cond*, *case*) that control the branches defined by function parameter values, with pattern-matching features and multi-clause functions. More details and code examples here: [\[LINK\]](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Alias expansion]**.

This refactoring aims to expand multi-alias instructions fused into one (e.g., *alias Foo.Bar (Baz, Boom)*), transforming them into separate alias instructions (e.g., *alias Foo.Bar Baz* and *alias Foo.Bar.Boom*). More details and code examples here: [\[LINK\]](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Add type declarations and contracts]**.

This refactoring aims to create custom data types using Elixir *typespecs*, thereby naming recurring data structures in the codebase. More details and code examples here: [\[LINK\]](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Move expression out of Case]**.

This refactoring restructures functions that use the divide-and-conquer pattern, making parallelization easier. To achieve this, it moves an expression outside of a "case" statement when it is repeated at the end of all branches. More details and code examples here: [\[LINK\]](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Introduce overloading]**.

This refactoring allows for the creation of a variation of a function (i.e., function with identical name but different arity or multi-clause function), enabling its use in different contexts. More details and code examples here: [\[LINK\]](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Transform nested "if" statements into a "cond"]**.

This refactoring aims to transform multiple nested "if" statements, used to compensate for the absence of the "else if" construct in Elixir, into the use of a logically equivalent "cond" statement. More details and code examples here: [\[LINK\]](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Modifying keys in a Map]**.

Sometimes we need to replace the name given to a key in a *Map* while retaining the association of the new key name with the original value. With this purpose in mind, this refactoring aims to replace the combined usage of the functions *Map.get/2*, *Map.put/2*, and *Map.delete/2* with a single *Map.new/2* call and a multi-clause lambda. More details and code examples here: [\[LINK\]](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Remove import attributes]**.

This refactoring allows removing the import directives in a module, replacing all calls to imported functions with fully-qualified name calls (i.e., *Module.function(args)*). More details and code examples here: [\[LINK\]](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Inline macro]**.

This refactoring aims to replace instances of macros with the code defined in their bodies. It can be useful when a macro is implemented to solve problems that functions or other pre-existing Elixir structures could solve. More details and code examples here: [\[LINK\]](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Transform "unless" with negated conditions into "if"]**.

This refactoring aims to replace "unless" statements with negated conditions with "if" statements. The reason is not technical but human-centric, because comprehending that something is executed only when a negated condition is not met is confusing. More details and code examples here: [\[LINK\]](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Rename an identifier]**.

This refactoring aims to rename an identifier (e.g., *function*, *module*, *variable*, etc.) to more meaningful names for humans. More details and code examples here: [\[LINK\]](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Generalise a function definition]**.

This refactoring aims to create a new higher-order function to generalize different functions that have equivalent expression structures. More details and code examples here: [\[LINK\]](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Nested list functions to comprehension]**.

This refactoring (a.k.a. deforestation) aims to transform nested calls to *Enum.map/2* and *Enum.filter/2* into a list comprehension (i.e., *for* construct), creating a semantically equivalent code that can be more readable and more efficient. This transformation avoids multiple traversals over a data structure and intermediate lists. More details and code examples here: [\[LINK\]](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Voltar

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Final remarks

Do you want to receive the preliminary results of this study? *

Yes

No

Please add here any comment about our work and survey:

Sua resposta

Uma cópia das suas respostas será enviada para o endereço de e-mail fornecido

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